

Reinforcement learning in the financial sector

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1. Introduction

Advanced Reinforcement learning techniques can be applied to much wider range of problems outside of what we usually come to think of, like gaming, self driving cars and robots. We showcase a solution that addresses multiple problems in relation to the banking world.

2. Aim

To introduce a framework for RL strategies to be applied in the financial sector towards a digitally complete customer strategy.

3. Material and methods

The research lab we setup as a collaboration between ATB Financial and the University of Alberta uses a range of advanced Reinforcement learning techniques, such as Contextual Multiarmed Bandits with Deep neural networks and Bayesian methods in conjunction with robust policy optimization approaches. These are used in order to be able to control risk in the arrived upon decision policy.

4. Results

We are implementing a complete customer strategy for retail financial customers at ATB driven by reinforcement learning models through the bank's digital channels. The RL engine is purposed to be running in the background and powering multiple interfaces within ATB optimizing the bank's decisions to adjust for increased customer satisfaction both financially and experientially as well as growth for the bank.

5. Conclusions

The presence of large amounts of digitally available customer data allows the utilization of advanced RL/ML techniques to make banking work better for people.

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6. Keywords

Reinforcement learning; Machine learning; CMAB; Deep learning; gamification; banking; financial advice

Author biography

Mark Sebestyen completed his MSc. in Pure Mathematics at the University of Alberta. After graduating he started applying his mathematical knowledge in the area of machine learning. He participated in theoretical RL/ML research at the University of Alberta after which he was working at one of Canadas fastest growing big-data startup companies at the time, where he was in charge of optimization and architecture of the companies AI/ML algorithms. Currently working for ATB Financial Mark is leading a couple AI-research labs which are part of a collaboration project between the University of Alberta and ATB.